

Supplementary Materials for

Phytogeographic history of the Tea family inferred through high-resolution phylogeny and fossils

*Yujing Yan^{1,2}, *Charles C. Davis², Dimitar Dimitrov^{1,3}, Zhiheng Wang⁴, Carsten Rahbek^{5,1,4,6,7}, Michael Krabbe Borregaard¹

1. Center for Macroecology, Evolution and Climate, GLOBE Institute, University of Copenhagen, Universitetsparken 15, 2100, Copenhagen, Denmark

2. Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Harvard University Herbaria, 22 Divinity Ave, Cambridge, MA 02138, USA

3. Department of Natural History, University Museum of Bergen, University of Bergen, P.O. Box 7800, 5020 Bergen, Norway

4. Institute of Ecology, College of Urban and Environmental Sciences, Key Laboratory of Earth Surface Processes of Ministry of Education, Peking University, Beijing 100871, China

5. Center for Global Mountain Biodiversity, GLOBE Institute, University of Copenhagen, Universitetsparken 15, 2100 Copenhagen, Denmark

6. Department of Life Sciences, Imperial College London, Silkwood Park campus, Ascot SL5 7PY, UK

7. Danish Institute for Advanced Study, University of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark.

*** Correspondence to:** Yujing Yan, email: africarugu@gmail.com or Charles C. Davis, email: cdavis@oeb.harvard.edu

This PDF file includes:

Appendix 1 (p.4)

Supplementary Notes 1 (p. 2-4)

Supplementary Tables S1 to S11 (p.7-42)

Supplementary Figures S1 to S10 (p.43-52)

Supplementary Note 1.

Inference of biogeographical patterns using a fully Bayesian method in RevBayes

We applied an alternative biogeographic method proposed by Landis et al. (2020) to a subset of our Theaceae empirical dataset and compared its performance to our method. This method uses a hierarchical Bayesian approach to account for the uncertainty in the position of fossils (lack of characters), phylogenetic relationships, and the geological/biogeographic template at once. The method takes a combined evidence strategy which “favors evolutionary histories that are in harmony across phylogenetic, temporal, biogeographic, and ecological components, while penalizing those with dissonant components” (Landis et al., 2020). However, because the method is computationally intensive, we only applied it to the Stewartieae clade.

Methods

-Dataset

We subset our Theaceae dataset to include the sampled 12 extant species and five fossil species of the tribe Stewartieae. The alignment length and partition scheme were the same as the full dataset.

-Implementation of the RevBayes method

This method combines a molecular substitution model to estimate the molecular variation, a fossilized birth-death model to account for the relationship between lineage diversification and fossil occurrence, and a DEC model to reconstruct the biogeographic history. We followed Landis et al. (2020) to set the molecular substitution model and the fossilized birth-death model. To shorten the computation, we first estimated the topology using the maximum likelihood method in RAxML with 1000 bootstraps. Then we pruned the estimated best tree to only include nodes that have a bootstrap value of 100. This tree was then used as a backbone tree to constrain the topology of extant species in the RevBayes analysis.

We set the prior on the root age of Stewartieae clade as a normal distribution which centered at 27.8 Ma and had an upper and lower boundary of 8.1 Ma and 125 Ma respectively. The maximum range occupation was set to two.

We have run two analyses. One used a time-stratified dispersal matrix which only allows the dispersal between Eurasia and Nearctic before 10Ma (corresponding to the M1 scenario in the BioGeoBEARS analysis), the other used the same dispersal matrix for all periods (corresponding to the M0 scenario in the BioGeoBEARS analysis).

The analyses were running with a sampling frequency of one tree every 50 generations until the ESS for estimated parameters become > 300 .

-Implementation of the empirical Bayesian method

Because BioGeoBEARS is a globally optimum model, we repeated our pipeline on the Stewartieae clade to eliminate potential differences associated with the use of different datasets. We used *Gordonia* as outgroup and reran the RAxML+TreePL step. We used two dating schemes. The first is assuming that the oldest fossil of the tribe with a detailed description, *Stewartia tertertia*, is a crown member of the Stewartieae clade. Under this assumption, we used the species to calibrate the crown node of Stewartieae. The second dating scheme is the same as in the main text, assuming that this fossil can only be used to calibrate the stem of the Stewartieae clade. It is not certain whether *Stewartia tertertia* belongs to the stem or crown of the group because its morphological characters are similar to *Stewartia malacodendorn*.

We found that the two dating schemes resulted in similar divergence time estimates. We used the phylogenies estimated under the first dating scheme in the following biogeographic analysis. The rest steps were the same as in the main text. We used only the DEC model with maximum ranges set to two. We summarized the proportions of phylogenies with each ancestral state and compared the results with the summarized posterior distribution of biogeographic reconstructions obtained with RevBayes.

Results and discussion

The results of divergence time estimates are shown in Fig. N1. The estimates using the approach in Landis et al. (2020) were generally in agreement with that using a penalized method. The only exception was the age of crown Stewartieae estimated under a non-stratified dispersal matrix. This estimate (c.38Ma) was much older than any previous estimates (Yu et al. 2017; Lin et al. 2019) and is less likely (Fig. N1). It is possibly a result of placing fossil species *Stewartia tertertia* on the stem of Stewartieae except *Stewartia malacodendorn* and employing the fossilized birth-death process. On the other hand, our penalized dating method is less sensitive to the placement of *Stewartia tertertia* and steadily estimated a crown node age between 20–30 Ma (Fig. N2), similar to our result in the main text (Fig. 2) and previous estimations (Yu et al. 2017; Lin et al. 2019).

The results of ancestral range reconstruction are shown in Fig. N3. The two methods are generally in congruence with each other, giving similar estimates of different ancestral states for the three key nodes. The only exception is still the crown node of Stewartieae under the non-stratified dispersal scenario. Our method estimated the states supported by most sampled phylogenies to be Eurasian, while RevBayes estimated the states to be Eurasian and Nearctic.

Figure N1. Dated phylogeny estimated in RevBayes using (a) a non-stratified dispersal matrix, (b) a stratified dispersal matrix. Bars indicate 95% highest posterior density. Red bars represent fossil species.

Figure N2. Dated phylogeny estimated in TreePL using *Stewartia tertiaryaria* to calibrate (a) the crown node of Stewartieae (b) the stem node of Stewartieae. Bars indicated 95% confidence intervals.

Figure N3. Comparison of the posterior probabilities estimated in RevBayes and the conditional probabilities (proportions of sampled phylogenies) estimated using our method of the same ancestral states of the three key nodes (crown Stewartieae, crown *Hartia*, and crown of strict *Stewartia*). The results are under (a) non-stratified dispersal scenario, and (b) stratified dispersal scenario. The dotted line in each plot represents a 1:1 line.

References

- Landis M.J., Eaton D.A.R., Clement W.L., Park B., Spriggs E.L., Sweeney P.W., Edwards E.J., Donoghue M.J. 2020. Joint Phylogenetic Estimation of Geographic Movements and Biome Shifts during the Global Diversification of *Viburnum*. *Syst. Biol.* 70:67–85.
- Lin H.-Y., Hao Y.-J., Li J.-H., Fu C.-X., Soltis P.S., Soltis D.E., Zhao Y.-P. 2019. Phylogenomic conflict resulting from ancient introgression following species diversification in *Stewartia* s.l. (Theaceae). *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* 135:1–11.
- Yu X.Q., Gao L.M., Soltis D.E., Soltis P.S., Yang J.B., Fang L., Yang S.X., Li D.Z. 2017b. Insights into the historical assembly of East Asian subtropical evergreen broadleaved forests revealed by the temporal history of the tea family. *New Phytol.* 215:1235–1248.

Appendix 1. Distribution data sources

- Enquist, B. J. et al. (2009). The Botanical Information and Ecology Network (BIEN): cyberinfrastructure for an integrated botanical information network to investigate the ecological impacts of global climate change on plant biodiversity. – The iPlant Collaborative, <www.iplantcollaborative.org/sites/default/files/BIEN_White_paper.pdf>
- Global biodiversity information facility (GBIF): <http://www.gbif.org/>. doi: 10.15468/dl.bpj2hf
- IDigBio. (2018). Integrated digitized biocollections. National Science Foundation. <https://www.idigbio.org/>.
- Ma K, Xu Z (2019). NSII (China National Specimen Information Infrastructure). Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS). <http://www.nsii.org.cn/>
- Min T, Bartholomew B. (2007). Theaceae. In *Flora of China*, pp. 366–478.
- NSII (National Specimen Information Infrastructure): <http://www.nsii.org.cn/>

Supplementary tables

- Table S1.** List of Genbank sequences used in the study
- Table S2.** List of taxa sampled in this study with voucher, distribution and assembly information
- Table S3.** Information of extracted coding regions of plastomes
- Table S4.** Rogue taxa identified using RogueNaRok in the combined plastome-nrDNA dataset.
- Table S5.** Node age calibration settings used in TreePL
- Table S6.** Dispersal matrix settings used in BioGeoBEARS for the M0 and M1 scenarios
- Table S7.** Information of fossils incorporated in the biogeographic analysis.
- Table S8.** Comparison of the estimated ages of selected nodes obtained in this and previous studies
- Table S9.** Comparison of DEC and DEC_j models for different datasets with maximum range size set to three.
- Table S10.** Comparison of biogeographic stochastic mapping result of main crown nodes across 300 phylogenies with maximum range size set to two.
- Table S11.** Comparison of biogeographic stochastic mapping result of main crown nodes across 300 phylogenies with maximum range size set to three.

Supplementary figures

Figure S1. Flowchart of the empirical Bayesian pipeline used in this study.

Figure S2. Maximum likelihood (ML) bipartition tree inferred from the plastid coding regions matrix. Numbers associated with nodes indicate ML bootstrap support (BS)/Bayesian inference (BI) posterior probability (PP) values. Asterisks mark nodes with the highest support using both methods (bootstrap value 100% and posterior probability 1.0).

Figure S3. Maximum likelihood (ML) bipartition tree inferred from the nrDNA matrix. Numbers associated with nodes indicate ML bootstrap support (BS)/Bayesian inference (BI) posterior probability (PP) values. Asterisks mark nodes with the highest support using both methods (bootstrap value 100% and posterior probability 1.0).

Figure S4. a) 50% consensus phylogeny of the randomly sampled 300 phylogenies with 10 fossil taxa added. b) The age interval of the added fossil taxa and the 95% confidence intervals of the estimated age of their corresponding genera and tribes.

Figure S5. Biogeographic reconstruction with DEC+j model under M0 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree based on only extant taxa (a) or based on both extant taxa and 10 fossil taxa (b). Colored circles at tips represent current ranges. Pie charts at inner nodes represent the average marginal probability of ranges across the 300 phylogenies and probabilities lower than 0.1 were combined and shown in white. Periods of forest types are divided following Meseguer et al. (2015). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using only extant taxa (c) or using both extant and 10 extinct taxa (d). One tick mark represents one dispersal event. The lower panel show the source ranges and the upper panel show the sink ranges. The colored band within the lower panel show the sink ranges for each source range.

Figure S6. Biogeographic reconstruction with DEC model under M1 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. Annotations are the same as in Figure S6. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree based on only extant taxa (a) or based on both extant taxa and 10 fossil taxa (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using only extant taxa (c) or using both extant and 10 extinct taxa (d).

Figure S7. Biogeographic reconstruction with DEC+j model under M1 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree based on only extant taxa (a) or based on both extant taxa and 10 fossil taxa (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using only extant taxa (c) or using both extant and 10 extinct taxa (d).

Figure S8. Biogeographic reconstruction incorporating information of 22 fossils under M0 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree using DEC model (a) or using DEC+j model (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using DEC model (c) or using DEC+j model (d).

Figure S9. Biogeographic reconstruction incorporating information of 22 fossils under M1 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree using DEC model (a) or using DEC+j model (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using DEC model (c) or using DEC+j model (d).

Figure S10. The biogeographic reconstruction of the best tree using a reduced ancestral state space under M0 scenario using DEC model. Only adjacent ranges or single range were allowed (ES, EN, SM, NP, E, S, N, M, P).

Table S1. List of Genbank sequences used in this study (pt = plastomes, nr = nrDNA)

Data Type	Accession	Family	Taxon (Genbank)	References
nr	MF171070.1	Ebenaceae	<i>Diospyros dumetorum</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171071.1	Ebenaceae	<i>Diospyros strigosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171076.1	Lecythidaceae	<i>Barringtonia fusicarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171077.1	Lecythidaceae	<i>Barringtonia racemosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171084.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Adinandra angustifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171085.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Adinandra millettii</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171086.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Anneslea fragrans</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171078.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Pentaphylax euryoides</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171081.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Ternstroemia gymnanthera</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171075.1	Sladeniaceae	<i>Sladenia celastrifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171073.1	Styracaceae	<i>Meliiodendron xylocarpum</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171074.1	Styracaceae	<i>Sinojackia rehderiana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171072.1	Styracaceae	<i>Styrax grandiflorus</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171079.1	Symplocaceae	<i>Symplocos costaricana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171080.1	Symplocaceae	<i>Symplocos paniculata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171098.1	Theaceae	<i>Apterosperma oblata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171090.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia elongata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171087.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia mairei</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171088.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia oleifera</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171089.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia reticulata</i>	Yu et al., 2017

nr	AF315492.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Tang et al., 2000
nr	JN007223.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Xu et al., 2015
nr	MF171091.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia szechuanensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171100.1	Theaceae	<i>Franklinia alatamaha</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171101.1	Theaceae	<i>Gordonia brandegeei</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171102.1	Theaceae	<i>Gordonia lasianthus</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171099.1	Theaceae	<i>Laplacea fruticosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171082.1	Theaceae	<i>Polyspora axillaris</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171083.1	Theaceae	<i>Polyspora hainanensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171108.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria diospyricarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171107.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria jonquieriana subsp. multisejala</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171109.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria khasiana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171110.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria menglaensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171120.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria microcarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171111.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria oblongicarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171121.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria pingpienensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171118.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria spectabilis var. greeniae</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171112.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima brevipedicellata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171113.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima noronhae</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171114.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima sericans</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171116.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima superba</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171115.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima wallichii</i>	Yu et al., 2017

nr	MF171106.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia calcicola</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171103.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia cordifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171104.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia crassifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171094.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia malacodendron</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171095.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia ovata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171096.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia pseudocamellia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171105.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia pteropetiolata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171093.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia rostrata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171097.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia rubiginosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171092.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia sinensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171117.1	Theaceae	<i>Tutcheria championii</i>	Yu et al., 2017
nr	MF171119.1	Theaceae	<i>Tutcheria hirta</i> var. <i>cordatula</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179487.1	Ebenaceae	<i>Diospyros dumetorum</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179495.1	Ebenaceae	<i>Diospyros strigosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179485.1	Lecythidaceae	<i>Barringtonia fusicarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179489.1	Lecythidaceae	<i>Barringtonia racemosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179491.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Adinandra angustifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179492.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Adinandra millettii</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179497.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Anneslea fragrans</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_039178.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Euryodendron excelsum</i>	Shi et al., 2018
pt	MF179498.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Pentaphylax euryoides</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179490.1	Pentaphylacaceae	<i>Ternstroemia gymnanthera</i>	Yu et al., 2017

pt	NC_021121.1	Primulaceae	<i>Ardisia polysticta</i>	Ku et al., 2013
pt	NC_026197.1	Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia coreana</i>	Son & Park, 2016
pt	NC_024543.1	Primulaceae	<i>Primula poissonii</i>	Yang et al., 2014
pt	MF179494.1	Sladeniaceae	<i>Sladenia celastrifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179500.1	Styracaceae	<i>Meliiodendron xylocarpum</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179499.1	Styracaceae	<i>Sinojackia rehderiana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179493.1	Styracaceae	<i>Styrax grandiflorus</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179496.2	Symplocaceae	<i>Symplocos costaricana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	MF179486.1	Symplocaceae	<i>Symplocos paniculata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035641.1	Theaceae	<i>Apterosperma oblata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY856741.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia azalea</i>	Xu et al., 2017
pt	NC_024541.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia crapnelliana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_022459.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia cuspidata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_022460.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia danzaiensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035652.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia elongata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KJ806274.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia grandibracteata</i>	Huang et al., 2014
pt	MH394404.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia gymnogyna</i>	Zeng et al., 2018
pt	KY626040.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia huana</i>	Wang et al., 2017
pt	NC_022461.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia impressinervis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_024660.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia leptophylla</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY626041.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia liberofilamenta</i>	Wang et al., 2017
pt	KY626042.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia luteoflora</i>	Wang et al., 2017

pt	NC_035688.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia mairei</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406750.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia oleifera</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_024661.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia petelotii</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_022462.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia pitardii</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KJ806277.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia pubicosta</i>	Huang et al., 2014
pt	KY406793.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia reticulata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KF562708.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> cultivar <i>Longjing 43</i>	Ye et al., 2013
pt	JQ975030.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> var. <i>assamica</i>	Shi et al., 2013
pt	KJ806279.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> var. <i>dehungensis</i>	Huang et al., 2014
pt	KJ806280.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> var. <i>pubilimba</i>	Huang et al., 2014
pt	KJ806281.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> var. <i>sinensis</i>	Huang et al., 2014
pt	NC_035651.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia szechuanensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406759.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia tachangensis</i> var. <i>remotiserrata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_022264.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia taliensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_022463.1	Theaceae	<i>Camellia yunnanensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035692.1	Theaceae	<i>Franklinia alatamaha</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035646.1	Theaceae	<i>Gordonia brandegeei</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035699.1	Theaceae	<i>Gordonia lasianthus</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035700.1	Theaceae	<i>Laplacea fruticosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035645.1	Theaceae	<i>Polyspora axillaris</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406769.1	Theaceae	<i>Polyspora dalgleishiana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035693.1	Theaceae	<i>Polyspora hainanensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017

pt	NC_035689.1	Theaceae	<i>Polyspora longicarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035643.1	Theaceae	<i>Polyspora speciosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035704.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria diospyricarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406785.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria hirta</i> var. <i>cordatula</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406771.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria hirta</i> var. <i>hirta</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406772.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria jonquieriana</i> subsp. <i>multisepala</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035644.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria khasiana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035639.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria menglaensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035686.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria microcarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035694.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria oblongicarpa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035642.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria pingpienensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406757.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria spectabilis</i> var. <i>greeniae</i> voucher YangSX 4360	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406753.1	Theaceae	<i>Pyrenaria spectabilis</i> var. <i>greeniae</i> voucher YXQ172	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035537.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima brevipedicellata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035538.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima crenata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035539.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima khasiana</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035540.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima multibracteata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035541.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima noronhae</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035542.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima remotiserrata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035543.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima sericans</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035544.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima sinensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035545.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima superba</i>	Yu et al., 2017

pt	NC_035546.1	Theaceae	<i>Schima wallichii</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035696.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia calcicola</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035649.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia cordifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035647.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia crassifolia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035691.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia malacodendron</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035695.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia ovata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	KY406786.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia pseudocamellia</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035690.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia pteropetiolata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035698.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia rostrata</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035650.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia rubiginosa</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035640.1	Theaceae	<i>Stewartia sinensis</i>	Yu et al., 2017
pt	NC_035687.1	Theaceae	<i>Tutcheria championii</i>	Yu et al., 2017

References

- Huang, H., Shi, C., Liu, Y., Mao, S.-Y., & Gao, L.-Z. (2014). Thirteen *Camellia* chloroplast genome sequences determined by high-throughput sequencing: genome structure and phylogenetic relationships. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, *14*(1), 151. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-14-151>
- Ku C., Hu J.-M., Kuo C.-H. 2013. Complete plastid genome sequence of the basal asterid *Ardisia polysticta* Miq. and comparative analyses of Asterid plastid genomes. *PLoS One*. 8:e62548.
- Shi, C., Liu, Y., Huang, H., Xia, E. H., Zhang, H. Bin, & Gao, L. Z. (2013). Contradiction between plastid gene transcription and function due to complex posttranscriptional splicing: an exemplary study of *ycf15* function and evolution in angiosperms. *PLoS ONE*, *8*(3). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0059620>
- Son Og., Park S.J. 2016. Complete chloroplast genome sequence of *Lysimachia coreana* (Primulaceae). *Mitochondrial DNA. Part A, DNA mapping, Seq. Anal.* *27*:2263–2265.
- Wang G, Luo Y, Hou N, Deng LX (2017) The complete chloroplast genomes of three rare and endangered camellias (*Camellia huana*, *C. liberofilamenta* and *C. luteoflora*) endemic to Southwest China. *Conserv Genet Resour.* doi:10.1007/s12686-017-0727-z
- Xu J., Xu Y., Yonezawa T., Li L., Hasegawa M., Lu F., Chen J., Zhang W. 2015. Polymorphism and evolution of ribosomal DNA in tea (*Camellia sinensis*, Theaceae). *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* *89*:63–72.
- Xu, X., Zheng, W., & Wen, J. (2017). The complete chloroplast genome of the long blooming and critically endangered *Camellia azalea*. *Conservation Genetics Resources*, *0*(0), 0. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12686-017-0749-6>
- Yang J.-B., Li D.-Z., Li H.-T. 2014. Highly effective sequencing whole chloroplast genomes of angiosperms by nine novel universal primer pairs. *Mol. Ecol. Resour.* *14*
- Yang, J. B., Yang, S. X., Li, H. T., Yang, J., & Li, D. Z. (2013). Comparative chloroplast genomes of *Camellia* species. *PLoS ONE*, *8*(8). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0073053>

- Yu, X. Q., Drew, B. T., Yang, J. B., Gao, L. M., & Li, D. Z. (2017). Comparative chloroplast genomes of eleven *Schima* (Theaceae) species: Insights into DNA barcoding and phylogeny. *PLoS ONE*, *12*(6), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0178026>
- Yu, X. Q., Gao, L. M., Soltis, D. E., Soltis, P. S., Yang, J. B., Fang, L., Yang S.X., Li, D. Z. (2017). Insights into the historical assembly of East Asian subtropical evergreen broadleaved forests revealed by the temporal history of the tea family. *New Phytologist*, *215*(3), 1235–1248.
- Zeng, C. X., Hollingsworth, P. M., Yang, J., He, Z. S., Zhang, Z. R., & Li, D. Z. (2018). Genome skimming herbarium specimens for DNA barcoding and phylogenomics. *Plant Methods*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13007-018-0300-0>

Table S2. List of taxa sampled in this study with voucher, distribution and assembly information. Herbarium abbreviations are as follows: HUH = Harvard University Herbaria, NYBG = New York Botanical Garden. A hyphen (-) in the list of mean coverage indicates cases where sequences that did not pass the quality check.

Taxon	Voucher	Collected Year	Collected Location	Herbaria	No. reads (trimmed)	pt-mean coverage	nr-mean coverage
<i>Camellia amplexifolia</i>	F.C.How 72785	1935	Hainan, China	HUH	3875961	7	432
<i>Camellia assimilis</i>	C.P.Lau 40	2002	Hongkong, China	HUH	2211810	18	298
<i>Camellia assimiloides</i>	Tsang, W.T. 23506	1934	Hunan, China	HUH	1100104	14	78
<i>Camellia brachyandra</i>	C.Wang 34033	1933	Hainan, China	HUH	866289	6	23
<i>Camellia brevistyla</i>	D.E.Boufford & B.Bartholomew 25080	1989	Taiwan, China	HUH	1719689	12	120
<i>Camellia buxifolia</i>	C.Chow	1941	Emeishan, China	HUH	16514424	31	52022
<i>Camellia caudata</i>	B.Bartholomew 7648	1997	Taiwan, China	HUH	7845222	55	458
<i>Camellia chekiangoleosa</i>	Lau, S.K. 4389	1934	China	HUH	569423	170	56
<i>Camellia confusa</i>	C.W.Wang No. 75687	1936	Yunnan, China	HUH	3151479	15	576
<i>Camellia cordifolia</i>	Taam, Y.W. No. 173	1937	Guangdong, China	HUH	965326	88	46
<i>Camellia costei</i>	Y. Tsiang No. 5302	1930	Guizhou, China	HUH	3567674	29	97
<i>Camellia euryoides</i>	J.Wen 9357	2006	China	HUH	2309844	53	302
<i>Camellia fluviatilis</i>	S.K.Lau 28372	1936	Hainan, China	HUH	349210	-	3733
<i>Camellia forrestii</i>	T.T.Yu 16242	1938	Yunnan, China	HUH	1734061	15	142
<i>Camellia fraterna</i>	K.S.Chow 97	1973	Anhui, China	HUH	3348386	21	506
<i>Camellia furfuracea</i>	H.Y.Liang 69464	1937	Guangdong, China	HUH	3383789	23	79
<i>Camellia gracilipes</i>	J & M.S.Clemens 3310	1927	Vietnam	HUH	2602060	20	142
<i>Camellia granthamiana</i>	Shui Ying Hu 6122	1968	Hongkong, China	HUH	12850306	169	1683

<i>Camellia handelii</i>	Luo-Linbo 273	1994	Hunan, China	HUH	443513	-	331
<i>Camellia hiemalis</i>	Gen Murata 99223	2009	Japan	HUH	4214291	51	473
<i>Camellia kissii</i>	Li Heng 10334	1998	Yunnan, China	HUH	1962201	8	96
<i>Camellia lanceolata</i>	John H. Beaman 8349	1984	Java, Indonesia	HUH	1869252	13	258
<i>Camellia lancilimba</i>	Tsang, W.T. 25009	1935	Guangdong, China	HUH	13176350	29	42604
<i>Camellia liberistyla</i>	K.M.Feng 11264	1947	Yunnan, China	HUH	577464	-	45
<i>Camellia longicarpa</i>	T.C.Lee 4482	1940	Sichuan, China	HUH	1039880	-	31
<i>Camellia lutchuensis</i>	Shigetomo Yonemori TUSw-10002	1995	Japan	HUH	18200613	477	6733
<i>Camellia montana</i>	A.D.E.Elmer 18287	1917	Luzou,Philippine s	HUH	2190217	-	57
<i>Camellia obtusifolia</i>	Hui-yu Zou 760	1980	Zhejiang, China	HUH	759025	-	152
<i>Camellia pachyandra</i>	C.W.Wang 73204	1936	Yunnan, China	HUH	910022	7	54
<i>Camellia parviflora</i>	S.K.Lau No. 27055	1936	Hainan, China	HUH	205674	-	21
<i>Camellia parvilimba</i>	J.Linsley Gressitt 1601	1936	Jiangxi, China	HUH	1303324	17	114
<i>Camellia parvimuricata</i>	B.Bartholomew 913	1986	Guizhou, China	HUH	3763501	36	534
<i>Camellia paucipunctata</i>	N.K.Chun 44636	1932	Hainan, China	HUH	2686028	11	362
<i>Camellia rhytidocarpa</i>	Luo-Linbo No. 330	1994	Hunan, China	HUH	2307640	16	300
<i>Camellia rosthorniana</i>	W.P.Fang 5672	1928	Sichuan, China	HUH	3089560	17	172
<i>Camellia salicifolia</i>	Shiu Ying Hu 10511a	1970	Hong Kong, China	HUH	2646864	11	325
<i>Camellia saluenensis</i>	B.Bartholomew, D.E.Boufford, H.W.Li et al. 1370	1984	Yunnan, China	HUH	1710987	40	220
<i>Camellia transarisanensis</i>	Liang-Hung Wu 86	1996	Taiwan, China	HUH	2676145	40	208
<i>Camellia trichoclada</i>	Shui Ying Hu 13046	1973	Hongkong, China	HUH	2010566	54	205
<i>Camellia tsaii</i>	Li Heng 10784	1998	Yunnan, China	HUH	1561223	10	112

<i>Camellia tuberculata</i>	L.Y.Tai 651	1940	Sichuan, China	HUH	1751420	21	130
<i>Camellia uraku</i>	M.Mizushima 1831	1952	Japan	HUH	12187464	79	1278
<i>Camellia wardii</i>	Li Heng 11559	1998	Yunnan, China	HUH	2171651	26	205
<i>Camellia wenshanensis</i>	K.M.Feng 13739	1947	Yunnan, China	HUH	494249	13	7580
<i>Gordonia balansae</i>	S.K.Lau 28253	1936	Hainan, China	HUH	762479	-	50
<i>Gordonia gigantiflora</i>	M.Poilane 984	1929	Laos	HUH	1129737	25	81
<i>Gordonia haematoxylon</i>	Bro.Alain H. Liogier 13496	1968	Dominican Republic	HUH	2534644	75	607
<i>Gordonia haematoxylon</i>	Bro.Alain H. Liogier 15492	1969	Cuba	HUH	4223992	72	395
<i>Gordonia havilandii</i>	C.O.Webb CW 3403	1998	Pahang, Malaysia	HUH	2035199	29	331
<i>Gordonia imbricata</i>	T.G.Laman TL815	1997	Indonesia	HUH	366859	506	33
<i>Gordonia lasianthus</i>	T.G.Harbison 5935	1921	U.S.	HUH	15903045	508	54203
<i>Gordonia luzonica</i>	Nina R. Ingle 275	1998	Luzon, Philippines	HUH	2680525	118	808
<i>Gordonia marginata</i>	Church, A.C. 1796	1995	Indonesia	HUH	2625892	20	176
<i>Gordonia obtusa</i>	Pess 134	-	India	HUH	1017459	-	106
<i>Gordonia papuana</i>	W.Takeuchi 19429	2005	New Guinea	HUH	491540	174	77
<i>Gordonia sarawakensis</i>	Rosli S 14983	1961	Sabah, Malaysia	HUH	103548	35	13
<i>Gordonia singaporeana</i>	E.J.H.Cornier 33564	1937	Singapore	HUH	508648	-	689
<i>Gordonia szechuanensis</i>	G.Forrest 9237	-	China	HUH	1414198	4	39
<i>Gordonia tonkinensis</i>	J & M S Clemens 4257	1927	Annam, Indo-China	NYBG	603149	8	22
<i>Gordonia yunnanensis</i>	H.T.Tsai 61773	1934	Yunnan, China	HUH	2583363	13	741
<i>Laplacea angustifolia</i>	SM 10	2006	Granma, Cuba	NYBG	2693717	24	454
<i>Laplacea wrightii</i> var. <i>moaensis</i>	A. Urquiola, G. Zizka & S. Dressler 504	2006	Holguin, Cuba	NYBG	1449390	27	304

<i>Laplacea wrightii</i> var. <i>moaensis</i>	A. Urquiola, G. Zizka & S. Dressler 477	2006	Holguin, Cuba	NYBG	1243896	33	345
<i>Schima brevifolia</i>	Jose L. Panero 6367	1996	Sabah, Malaysia	NYBG	2575227	70	589
<i>Stewartia serrata</i>	T. Fujii et al., E324	1995	Kouchi, Japan	HUH	1842315	10	112

Table S3. Information of extracted coding regions of plastomes

Gene	Length	Gene	Length	Gene	Length
accD	1595	petB	680	rpl23	281
atpA	1523	petD	524	rpl32	191
atpB	1496	petG	113	rpl33	206
atpE	408	psaA	2252	rpl36	113
atpF1	156	psaB	2204	rpoA	1019
atpF2	471	psaC	390	rpoB	3226
atpH	245	psaI	110	rpoC1-1	455
atpI	743	psaJ	134	rpoC1-2	1637
ccsA	1139	psbA	1061	rpoC2	4218
cemA	701	psbB	1527	rps11	424
clpP1	289	psbC	1421	rps12	240
clpP2	308	psbD	1061	rps14	305
infA	233	psbE	251	rps15	323
matK	1544	psbF	119	rps16	230
ndhA1	582	psbH	233	rps18	305
ndhA2	741	psbI	166	rps19	278
ndhB1	777	psbJ	122	rps2	710
ndhB2	755	psbK	185	rps3	656
ndhC	362	psbL	116	rps4	608
ndhD	1803	psbM	116	rps7	467

ndhE	310	psbN	131	rps8	407
ndhF	2747	psbT	116	ycf1	6316
ndhG	590	psbZ-lhbA	188	ycf15	254
ndhH	1464	rbcL	1427	ycf2	6988
ndhI	575	rpl14	368	ycf3-1	124
ndhJ	477	rpl16	410	ycf3-2	227
ndhK	903	rpl2-1	399	ycf3-3	154
orf188	614	rpl2-2	434	ycf4	554
orf42	128	rpl20	380		
petA	962	rpl22	506		

Table S4. Rogue taxa identified using RogueNaRok in the combined plastome-nrDNA dataset.

Taxon	Raw improvement	RBIC
<i>Camellia handelii</i>	3.03	0.78
<i>Camellia longicarpa</i>	4.27	0.80
<i>Camellia yunnanensis</i>	1.03	0.81
<i>Camellia indochinensis</i>	1.08	0.82
<i>Camellia villicarpa</i>	0.96	0.82
<i>Camellia tsingpienensis</i>	0.92	0.83
<i>Gordonia obtusa</i>	0.34	0.83
<i>Camellia tachangensis</i> var. <i>remotiserrata</i>	0.18	0.83
<i>Schima superba</i>	0.02	0.83

Table S5. Fossils and node age calibration settings used in TreePL.

Calibration nodes	Fossils	Fossil types	Fossil ages (epoch)	Fossil assignment	Constrained age1	Constrained age2	Fossil literature
0	<i>Paradinandra suecica</i> Schönenberger & Friis <i>Visnea minima</i>	Flower	Late Santonian- Early Campanian	The age of the root	79.8a-109	79.8a-125	Schönenberger and Priis 2001
1	<i>Pentaphylax protogaea</i> Knobloch & Mai <i>Rehderodendron stonei</i> (Reid & Chandler) Mai	Fruit	Maastrichtian, Cretaceous	Stem of Pentaphylacace ae	66.0-109	66.0-125	Knobloch et al. 1986
2	<i>Andrewsiocarpon henryense</i> Grote and Dilcher	Fruit	Ypresian, Early Eocene	Stem of Styracaceae	47.8-109	47.8-125	Mai, 1970; Manchester et al. 2009
3	<i>Stewartia tertiaria</i> Mai	Fruits, seeds	Middle Eocene Upper Eocene to Middle Oligocene	Stem of Theaceae	37.8b-109	37.8b-125	Grote and Dilcher 1989
4	<i>Schima kwangsiensis</i>	Seeds	Middle Oligocene	Stem of Stewartia	27.8-109	27.8-125	D. H. Mai and H. Walther, 1978; Mai 1998
5	Shi <i>Hartia</i>	Fruits, seeds	Late Oligocene	Stem of Schima	23.0-109	23.0-125	Shi et al. 2017
6	<i>quinqueangularis</i> Mai	Fruits, seeds	Late Miocene	Crown of Hartia	5.3-109	5.3-125	Mai 1975

Note: For node 0-3 and 6, we used the same fossils as in (Yu et al. 2017). Their study shows that the influence of different root setting and the constrain of stems or crowns is minor and different settings yeild similar results. We conservatively calibrated the stem age using the same settings as in Yu et al. 2017. Because TreePL set the crown root age as the lowest bound of the constrain and this may have an impact on the age calibration, we still compared setting the lowest bound to 109Ma and 125Ma following Yu et al. 2017. The lower third of the Campanian was used as the possible uppermost bound for the root age (a) following Magallón et al. 2015 and same as Yu et al. 2017), and the upper boundary of the Middle Eocene was used (Schwery et al. 2015) for node 3(b). The stems of nodes 4 and 5 were calibrated using the oldest fossil found for each clade. *Stewartia tertiaria* used for node 4 are fossil seeds found from the Middle Oligocene of Germany. They have been assigned to *Stewartia* group based on morphology but are different from modern species (Mai 1998). *Schima kwangsiensis* used for node 5 are fossil fruit and seeds found from the upper Oligocene from the Yongning Formation of the Nanning Basin in China. Morphological comparison confidently placed this species in the group (Shi et al. 2017). However, the relationships reconstructed using fruit morphological evidence are not the same as those based on molecular evidence. Hence, we conservatively calibrate stem age using the fossils. Ages of stratigraphic boundaries were obtained from (Walker et al. 2018).

References

- Grote P., Dilcher D. 1989. Investigations of angiosperms from the Eocene of North America: A new genus of Theaceae based on fruit and seed remains. *Bot. Gaz.* 150:190–206.
- Knobloch E., Mai D.H., Holý F. 1986. Monographie der Früchte und Samen in der Kreide von Mitteleuropa : vorgelegt am 22 Oktober 1983, genehmigt am 25 Juni 1984. Praha : Vydal Ústřední ústav geologický v Academii, nakladatelství Československé akademie věd.
- Magallón S., Gómez-Acevedo S., Sánchez-Reyes L.L., Hernández-Hernández T. 2015. A metacalibrated time-tree documents the early rise of flowering plant phylogenetic diversity. *New Phytol.* 207:437–453.
- Mai DH. 1970. Subtropische Elemente im europäischen Tertiär I. Die Gattungen *Gironniera*, *Sarcococca*, *Illicium*, *Evodia*, *Ilex*, *Mastixia*, *Alangium*, *Symplocos* und *Rehderodendron*. . *Paläontologische Abhandlungen Abt. B* 3: 441–503, pls. 458–469.
- Mai DH. 1975. Über Früchte und Samen von *Hartia Dunn* (Theaceae). *Friedrich-Schiller-Univ. Jena, Math.-Nat.* 24: 463-476.
- Mai DH, Walther H. 1985. Die obereozänen Floren des Weißelster-Beckens und seiner Randgebiete. *Abh. Staatl. Mus. Min. Geol. Dresden* 33: 1-220.
- Mai D.H. 1998. Contribution to the flora of the middle Oligocene Calau Beds. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* 101:43–70.
- Manchester S.R., Chen Z.D., Lu A.M., Uemura K. 2009. Eastern Asian endemic seed plant genera and their paleogeographic history throughout the Northern Hemisphere. *J. Syst. Evol.* 47:1–42.
- Schönenberger J., Priis E.M. 2001. Fossil flowers of Ericalean affinity from the Late Cretaceous of Southern Sweden. *Am. J. Bot.* 88:467–480.
- Schwery O., Onstein R.E., Bouchenak-Khelladi Y., Xing Y., Carter R.J., Linder H.P. 2015. As old as the mountains: The radiations of the Ericaceae. *New Phytol.* 207:355–367.
- Shi X., Fu Q., Jin J., Quan C. 2017. Mummified Oligocene fruits of *Schima* (Theaceae) and their systematic and biogeographic implications. *Sci. Rep.* 7:4009.
- Walker D., Geissman J., Compilers. 2018. GSA Geologic time scale v. 5.0. *Geol. Soc. Am.* 204:59425.
- Yu X.Q., Gao L.M., Soltis D.E., Soltis P.S., Yang J.B., Fang L., Yang S.X., Li D.Z. 2017. Insights into the historical assembly of East Asian subtropical evergreen broadleaved forests revealed by the temporal history of the tea family. *New Phytol.* 215:1235–1248.

Table S6. Dispersal probability matrix used in BioGeoBEARS. Abbreviations of phyloregions are as follows: N = Nearctic, P = Panamanian, E = Eurasia, S = Sino-Japanese, M = Papua-Melanesia. The three periods were divided according to the existence of different vegetation types across the Northern Hemisphere in (Meseguer et al. 2015).

Dispersal scenario	Time period (Ma)	Region	E	N	P	M	S
M0	0-10	E	1	1	0.01	0.01	1
		N	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01
		P	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01
		M	0.01	0.01	0.01	1	0.01
		S	1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1
	10-35	E	1	1	0.01	0.01	1
		N	0.5	1	1	0.01	0.01
		P	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01
		M	0.01	0.01	0.01	1	0.01
		S	1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1
	35-90	E	1	1	0.01	0.01	1
		N	1	1	1	0.01	0.01
		P	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01
		M	0.01	0.01	0.01	1	0.01
		S	1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1
M1	0-10	E	1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1
		N	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01

	P	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01
	M	0.01	0.01	0.01	1	0.01
	S	1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1
	E	1	0.5	0.01	0.01	1
10-35	N	0.5	1	1	0.01	0.01
	P	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01
	M	0.01	0.01	0.01	1	0.01
	S	1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1
	E	1	1	0.01	0.01	1
35-90	N	1	1	1	0.01	0.01
	P	0.01	1	1	0.01	0.01
	M	0.01	0.01	0.01	1	0.01
	S	1	0.01	0.01	0.01	1

Reference

Meseguer A.S., Lobo J.M., Ree R., Beerling D.J., Sanmartín I. 2015. Integrating fossils, phylogenies, and niche models into biogeography to reveal ancient evolutionary history: The case of *Hypericum* (Hypericaceae). *Syst. Biol.* 64:215–232.

Table S7. Information of the fossil dataset incorporated in biogeographic analysis. Abbreviations of phyloregions are as follows: N = Nearctic, E = Eurasia, S = Sino-Japanese.

Fossil taxon	Fossil types	Fossil ages (epoch)	Age upper bounds	Age lower bounds	Country	Phylor egion	Taxonomic placement	Close extent species based on morphology	References	Reduced dataset
<i>Camelia kueishanensis</i>	Wood	Early Miocene	16	20.4	China	S	<i>Camellia</i>	Similar to <i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Li et al. 2003	
<i>Camellia japonoxyla</i>	Wood	Early Miocene	16	20.4	Japan	S	<i>Camellia</i>	Similar to <i>Camellia japonica</i>	Suzuki and Terada 1996	
<i>Camellia nanningensis</i>	Wood	Late Oligocene	23	27.8	China	S	<i>Camellia</i>	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> , <i>Camellia subacutissima</i> and <i>Camellia taliensis</i>	Huang et al. 2016	
<i>Gordonia emanuelii</i>	Leaf	Lower Pannonian, Late Miocene	5.3	11.6	Austria	E	<i>Polyspora</i>	More similar to Eastern Asia <i>Gordonia (Polyspora)</i>	Kovar-Ender and Hably 2006	Yes
<i>Gordonia hradekensis</i>	Leaf	Rupelian, Early Oligocene	27.8	33.9	Germany	E	<i>Polyspora</i>	More similar to Eastern Asia <i>Gordonia (Polyspora)</i>	Kvaček 2004	
<i>Gordonia pannonica</i>	Leaf	Lower Pannonian, Late Miocene	5.3	11.6	Austria	E	<i>Polyspora</i>	More similar to Eastern Asia <i>Gordonia (Polyspora)</i>	Kovar-Ender and Hably 2006	
<i>Gordonia pseudoknauensis</i>	Leaf	Rupelian, Early Oligocene	27.8	33.9	Germany	E	<i>Polyspora/ Theeae</i>	More similar to Eastern Asia <i>Gordonia (Polyspora)</i>	Kvaček 2004	Yes
<i>Gordonia stefanovii</i>	Leaf	Middle Miocene	11.6	16	Bulgaria	E	<i>Gordonia</i>	Similar to <i>Gordonia lasianthus</i>	Bozukov and Palamarev 1995	Yes
<i>Gordonia warmanensis</i>	Fruits, seeds	Middle Eocene	37.8	47.8	United States	N	<i>Gordonieae</i>	Intermedia between <i>Gordonia lasianthus</i> and Eastern Asia <i>Gordonia (Polyspora)</i>	Grote and Dilcher 1992	Yes
<i>Hartia palaeorhodopensis</i>	Leaf	Middle Miocene	11.6	16	Bulgaria	E	<i>Hartia</i>	Similar to <i>Hartia micrantha</i> and <i>Hartia yunnanensis</i>	Bozukov and Palamarev 1995	Yes
<i>Hartia quinqueangularis</i>	Fruits, seeds	Late Miocene	5.3	11.6	Germany	E	<i>Hartia</i>		Mai 1975	Yes
<i>Schima kwangsiensis</i>	Fruit	Late Oligocene	23	27.8	China	S	<i>Schima</i>	Similar to <i>Schima superba</i>	Shi et al. 2017	
<i>Schima mataschensis</i>	Leaf	Late Miocene	5.3	11.6	Austria	E	<i>Schima</i>		Kovar-Ender and Hably 2006	Yes

<i>Schima nanlinensis</i>	Fruits, seeds	Early Miocene	16	20.4	China	S	<i>Schima</i>	Similar to <i>Schima parviflora</i> and <i>Schima argentea</i>	Li et al. 2013	
<i>Schima protowallichii</i>	Wood	Miocene	5.3	23	Japan	S	<i>Schima</i>	Similar to <i>Schima wallichii</i>	Choi et al. 2010	
<i>Stewartia beckeriana</i>	Fruits	Early Pliocene	3.6	5.3	Germany	E	<i>Stewartia</i>	Similar to <i>Stewartia monadelpha</i>	Burgh 1983,	Yes
<i>Stewartia hokiana</i>	Leaf	Late Miocene	5.3	11.6	Japan	S	<i>Stewartia</i>		Ozaki 1980	
<i>Stewartia notoensis</i>	Wood	Early Miocene	16	20.4	Japan	S	<i>Stewartia</i>	Similar to <i>Stewartia pseudo-camillia</i>	Suzuki and Terada 1996	
<i>Stewartia pseudocamellioxylon</i>	Wood	Early Miocene	16	20.4	South Korea	S	<i>Stewartia</i>	Similar to <i>Stewartia pseudo-camillia</i>	Jeong et al. 2009	
<i>Stewartia stefanovii</i>	Leaf	Miocene	11.6	16	Bulgaria	E	<i>Stewartia</i>	Similar to <i>Stewartia ovata</i>	Palamarev 1995	Yes
<i>Stewartia submonadelpha</i>	Leaf	Miocene	11.6	16	Bulgaria	E	<i>Stewartia</i>	Similar to <i>Stewartia monadelpha</i>	Bozukov and Palamarev 1995	
<i>Stewartia tertiaria</i>	Seeds	Oligocene	27.8	33.9	Germany	E	<i>Stewartia</i>	Similar to <i>Stewartia sinensis</i>	Mai 1998	Yes

Note: Detailed description of fossils in the original literature and justifications of their affinities

Camelia kueishanensis:

This fossil is characterized by the following features. 1) wood diffuse-porous and evenly distributed, mostly solitary, small vessels; 2) perforation plates exclusively scalariform; 3) diffuse-in-aggregates and diffuse axial parenchyma; and 4) narrow heterocellular rays. Because of the number of bars per perforation plate, the rather low rays, and no crystals observed in either axial parenchyma cells or ray cells, the present fossil is similar to that of *Camellia* of the Theaceae. The fossil is similar to *C. sinensis* especially in the ray width and the lack of spiral thickening in vessels (Deng and Baas, 1991).

Camellia japonoxyla:

The occurrence of crystalliferous ray cells; possessing slightly larger vessels at the median part of growth ring increments, while the extant species show a tendency to be semi-ring-porous with larger vessels in the earlywood. The fossil has narrower rays (mostly 1 or 2 cells, rarely 3 cells wide), while the extant species have rays 1-3 cells in width. Therefore, the fossil was described as a new species of *Camellia*. It is similar to *C. japonica*, especially in the abundance of large crystalliferous ray cells.

Camellia nanningensis:

Vessels lumina mainly solitary and small, with tangential diameter up to 41 μm . Perforation plates exclusively scalariform, with up to 23 bars. Intervessel pits scalariform, occasionally transitional to opposite or alternate. Fibers non-septate, with distinctly bordered pits. Axial parenchyma diffuse, diffuse in aggregates and scantily paratracheal. Rays 1–2(3) seriate, heterocellular with 1–5 (up to 10) marginal rows of square and upright cells, sometimes with equally wide multiseriate and uniseriate portions. Vessel ray pits scalariform, with much reduced borders to simple. Crystals absent in axial parenchyma and ray cells. The combination of narrow vessel lumina ($<50 \mu\text{m}$ in tangential diameter) and mostly narrow (up to 3-seriate) rays, suggest the closest affinity of the fossil woods to the genus *Camellia*.

Gordonia emanuelii:

Coriaceous leaves, fragmentarily preserved, base acute, lamina possibly elliptic, no apex preserved, margin entire, possibly wavy or with single small teeth present, midvein stout, no further venation details discernible. Abaxial cuticle is thick, smooth, almost glabrous, along veins faint parallel cuticular striation; stomatal complexes anisocyclocytic with 3–6 narrow, tangentially elongated, intensively staining subsidiary cells surrounding the stomata; stomata roundish to oval, quite variable in size, 22–43 μm (27–35 μm) long, 22–34 μm (25–30 μm) wide, outer stomatal ledges of the guard cells distinctly thickened, smooth, stomatal aperture 8–26 μm (11–19 μm) long; prominent but short polar I-pieces present, often not reaching the poles, above the guard cells 1–2 concentric striae; size of non-modified epidermal cells 21–57 μm (28–40 μm), anticlines straight, curved to somewhat wavy, about 2 μm thick.

The fossil bears stomata of the “*Gordonia*-type” (Keng 1962). Tangentially more or less elongated and well-discernible subsidiary cells are mostly characteristic of *Gordonia* within the Theaceae. *Gordonia pseudoknauensis* Kvaček (Kvaček 2004) from Flörsheim is somewhat similar to *G. emanuelii*. However, *G. pseudoknauensis* differs by fewer and less distinctly developed subsidiary cells (3–4), more elliptic stomata, less distinct outer stomatal ledges, the spindle-like aperture with less well-developed polar I-shaped pieces. In *Gordonia hradekensis* (Kvaček & Bůžek) Palamarev & Bozukov the stomata more closely resemble *G. emanuelii*, being almost circular to broadly elliptic, showing well-thickened outer stomatal ledges forming an oval front cavity, and having well-developed polar I-pieces. However, *G. hradekensis* differs in the lower number of subsidiary cells (3–4), the presence of trichome bases, and the striae and wrinkles covering the abaxial cuticle (Kvaček & Walther 1984b, Kvaček 2004).

Gordonia hradekensis (= *Polyspora hradekensis*):

Leaf elongate, 10 mm wide, probably 55 mm long (48 mm preserved), subentire, with minute widely spaced sharp teeth (not observable by naked eye), margin thickened, apex broadly acute, base not preserved, cuneate, venation eucamptodromous to semicraspedodromous, not clearly discernible, midrib thin, slightly curved, secondaries steep, widely spaced, approaching closely the margin, higher-order venation not clearly discernible; texture coriaceous, adaxial cuticle thick, smooth, ordinary cells polygonal, 15–25 μm across, anticlines coarsely undulate with small thickenings in sinuses, solitary thick-walled starlike trichome bases with central simple pore, abaxial cuticle striate-wrinkled over the whole surface and concentrically wrinkled around stomata, ordinary cells polygonal, of variable size, anticlines coarsely undulate,

stomata anisocytic-cy- clocytic ("Gordonia-type"), guard cell pairs circular to broadly elliptic, typically 40 µm long, surrounded by 3- 4 uneven subsidiary cells in one circle, T-pieces in stomatal poles, ledges thickened all along the length, stomatal aperture broadly oval, fine granulate, trichome bases star-like, thickened, about 20 µm across, dispersed over the leaf underside.

A similar representative of this genus, probably an ancestor, is known from the Late Eocene as *Polyspora knauensis* (see Kvaček and Walther 1984b), and differs in straight- walled cells and very rare trichome bases. *G. hradekensis* occurs in the Miocene mastixioid assemblages. *Gordonia balansae* (= *Polyspora balansae*) from SE Asia has been suggested as a most likely extant analogue (Kvaček and Walther 1984b).

Gordonia pannonica:

Leaf fragments with acute/ acuminate bases, 3–5 slender veins arising at the base, running steeply across the lamina, sometimes forking. Abaxial cuticle thick, glabrous; stomatal complexes cyclocytic, subsidiaries tangentially elongated, covered by concentric wrinkles; stomata 22–39 µm (26–32 µm) long, 19–27 µm (23–25 µm) wide, epidermal walls and outer stomatal ledges of the guard cells distinctly thickened, smooth, stomatal aperture oval, 12–22 µm (14–18 µm) long, polar I-pieces more or less prominent; anticlines of the non-modified epidermal cells not visible; coarse, bundled, more or less parallel-running wrinkles strongly developed; wrinkles along veins oriented parallel to the elongated cell outlines. Following the determination key of Kvaček and Walther (1984a) for the Theaceae, these leaves are assigned to *Gordonia* not only based on the concentrically elongated subsidiary cells but also on the almost concentric wrinkles surrounding the stomata, and the wrinkles which are oriented in almost parallel bundles covering the areas between the stomatal complexes, and the smooth adaxial cuticle with curved and slightly undulating anticlines. The innermost circle of the concentric sculpturing of the stomatal complexes is situated above the guard cells. While the abaxial cuticle of *Gordonia emanuelii* exhibits a rather clear and regular appearance, that of *G. pannonica* is more irregular. This general appearance is largely caused by the wrinkles developed in *G. pannonica*. Although the stomata are almost equal in length, their width is smaller in *G. pannonica* (average 23–25 µm) than in *G. emanuelii* (average 25–30 µm). Further differences pertain to the adaxial cuticles, which show straight to slightly curved, even anticlines in *G. emanuelii* but curved to undulate, knobbed ones in *G. pannonica*.

Gordonia pseudoknauensis:

Leaves oblong elongate, 11-15 mm wide and probably more than 50 mm long (preserved maximum length 45 mm), margin with few widely spaced sharp teeth in the upper part of lamina, otherwise entire, apex not preserved, base widely cuneate, venation eucamptodromous to (? semi-) craspedodromous, midrib strong, straight, secondaries alternate, widely spaced, gently bent and looping very close to margin, or entering teeth, tertiary veins reticulate; texture coriaceous, adaxial cuticle thick, finely granulate, ordinary cells isodiametric, polygonal, 25-30 µm across, anticlines straight to bent, trichome bases thick cutinized, star-like, solitary on margin, abaxial cuticle thick, almost smooth except few wrinkles near stomata (SM. B 185c) to fine wrinkled all over the surface but not concentric around stomata (SM. B 176),

ordinary cells polygonal, 20-30 p.m across, anticlines wavy to undulate, stomata anisocytic, guard cell pairs broadly oval to roundish, 30-35 (in SM. B 176 up to 45) gm long, surrounded by 3-4 subsidiary cells uneven in size and slightly narrower than the ordinary cells, stomatal aperture broadly spindle-shaped, with medium thick ledges, pore slit-like, I-pieces thin, no trichome bases observed. Similar to *Gordonia knauensis* (= *Polyspora knauensis*) but distinct in having almost smooth abaxial cuticle and stomata without thickened ledges and T-pieces.

These leaves assigned to a new species of *Gordonia* can be distinguished from co-occurring *G. hradekensis* in having adaxially almost straight-walled cells, a much less distinct sculpture abaxially, stomata without concentric striation and polar T-pieces, and with only solitary trichome bases. The nearest living relatives of *G. pseudoknauensis* are spread in East Asia, e.g., *G. axillaris* (Kvaček and Walther 1984a).

Gordonia stefanovii:

Shape oblanceolate to narrow oblanceolate or narrow elliptic; base cuneate; margin of lamina toothed, teeth small, with long and strongly inclined basal side and very short apical one, with rounded tips. Venation semi-craspedodromous; midrib straight or slightly bent, thick, thinning towards the apex of lamina; secondary veins 17-22 pairs, arch-shaped, consecutive or opposite, forming an angle of about 50° with midrib and much thinner than it; intercalary veins frequent; tertiary veins hardly visible, where preserved forming among themselves a subtle polygonal reticulum. The lamina is (6.5-) 11.5-28.0 cm long and (1.6-)2.0-5.4 cm wide. Petiolus up to 2.7 cm in length and up to 0.3 cm in width. Some of the specimens studied show variations in the shape of the lamina and its dimensions but they comply with the intraspecific variation. The polymorphism observed with the contemporary analog supports that statement. The fossil species has a morphological similarity with the recent North American species *Gordonia lasianthus* Ellis (the southeastern regions of the USA), but it differs from it by the larger dimensions and the greater number of secondary veins.

Gordonia warmanensis:

This species is similar in morphology of the capsule to several Asian species of *Gordonia*, especially *G. obtusa* Wall. from India, which have narrowly elongate capsules and persistent sepals. As in the fossil, *G. obtusa* has valves that are longitudinally sulcate and small beaks on the apex of each valve. The sepals of the fossil are smaller than those of *G. obtusa*, however. *G. warmanensis* differs from *G. lamkinensis* in having rounded rather than oblique, triangular styler remnants and in having a central columella that is rounded at the apex rather than obtuse or nearly flat as in *G. lamkinensis*. An outer pericarp layer does not peel off as in *G. lamkinensis*. In addition, the seed body of *G. lamkinensis* is more vertical in position than that of *G. warmanensis* and does not appear to be concave ventrobasally.

The seeds are somewhat intermediate in shape between seeds of *Gordonia lasianthus* of southeastern North America and several Asian species, especially *G. chrysandra* Cowan from Yunnan, China. The concavity of the ventrobasal margin of *G. warmanensis* seeds are intermediate between the strong concavity of seeds of *G. lasianthus* and slight concavity of seeds of *G. chrysandra*. The seed body of *G. lasianthus* is covered with protuberances and ridges, forming an irregular margin in lateral view. The fossil seed, as well as the extant species observed other than *G. lasianthus*, have a smooth margin surrounding the seed body.

Hartia palaeorhodopensis:

Shape narrow elliptic, base slightly asymmetrical, cuneate; apex slightly acute; margin of lamina finely toothed, teeth with glands on their rounded tips are strongly inclined towards the lamina apex, the margin of lamina near the base is whole. Venations semicraspedodromous; midrib slightly arch-shaped, up to 1.0 mm thick at the base, strongly thinned towards the apex; secondary veins 8-10 pairs, consecutive, arch-shaped, forming an angle at 45-80° with midrib, that angle increasing from the first pair towards the leaf apex, joining either directly or through a system of arches; intercalary veins developed between most of secondary ones; tertiary veins undulate, forming between themselves irregular polygons and forming angles of 70-90° with the secondary ones.

The fossil material studied possesses great morphological resemblance with the Chinese representatives from genus *Hartia* - *H. micrantha* Chun and *H. yunnanensis* Hu, the first being distributed in the province of Kwangtung, and the second in Yunan.

Hartia quinqueangularis:

Although we did not have access to the original text by Mai 1975, this fossil was used in a recent study as calibration of crown *Hartia* (Yu et al., 2017). To ensure the comparability of this study with previous study, we also include this fossil in node calibration analysis and the following biogeographical analysis.

Schima kwangsiensis:

The new fossil species is characterized by its 5-loculed loculicidally dehiscent capsules, 5 imbricate sepals and pedicels with bracteoles. They have marginally winged seeds and persistent columellae extending most of the length of the locules. These fossil fruits belong to *Schima*. Compare with extant species, the new fossil species is distinguished by its longer pedicels, smaller sepals and larger globose fruits.

A cluster analysis using size of pedicel and sepal separate the fossil species to *S. wallichii* and *S. superba*. However, in our molecular phylogeny, *S. wallichii* was clustered with species with large sepals and the relationship differed from the character-based phylogeny.

Schima mataschensis:

Due to the strong wrinkles, the anticlines are hardly traceable, but the concentric wrinkles around the stomata suggest a cyclocytic arrangement of the subsidiaries and “*Gordonia*-type” stomata. Within the Theaceae and among those with “*Gordonia*-type” stomata, the genus *Schima* is the most likely candidate due to the strong, concentric wrinkles surrounding and even covering the stomata and the smoothly developed adaxial cuticle.

Schima nanlinensis:

A total of 6 complete fruits, 10 isolated vales or fragments and 5 in situ seeds were studied. Capsule is depressed globose, 6–9mm long and 8–11 mm wide. Fruit width/length ratio is 1.11–1.37. Pericarp is not fully dehiscent to release seeds, but only slightly dehiscent into five valves. Sepals are persistent, imbricate, surround the capsule, about 2 mm in diameter. Gynecium is superior indicated by the remains of calyx. Columella is persistent, stout and extending for two-thirds or more of locule length. Columella is apically five-angled, with an enlarged face inside each of the five locules. Seeds are still kept in locules and attached to the pericarp due to compression during preservation. They are reniform, flat, 6.5–7.5 mm long, 4.0–5.0 mm wide, sub-campylotropous orientated. Seed width/length ratio is 0.62–0.71. Seed has no clear membranous wing in the specimens, but shows curled margin. Pericarp is sclerenchymatous with tangentially elongate cells in cross-section.

Comparing with extant *Schima* species, they both have 5-loculed capsules with loculicidal dehiscence and remains of calyx at the base, as well as reniform flat seeds. However, seeds of extant *Schima* species show a marginal membranous wing, which is not clear in the fossil. But fossil seed is curled on margin, probably indicating the wing. The fossil also differs slightly from extant *Schima* species and known fossil fruits related to *Schima* in the shape and size of capsules.

Schima protowallichii:

This fossil wood is characterized by 1) somewhat indistinct growth rings, 2) diffuse porosity with mostly evenly distributed solitary small vessels, 3) scalariform perforation plates with 4 to 12 bars, 4) scalariform or opposite intervessel pits, 5) weakly heterocellular or rather homocellular, and mostly uniseriate, rarely biseriate rays, 6) the axial parenchyma is diffuse-in-aggregates and in uniseriate tangential bands, and 7) helical thickenings at the tips of vessels.

Woods with uniseriate or rarely biseriate rays, and scalariform perforation plates with a relatively low number of 4 to 12 bars, are found in the genera *Schima* (Theaceae) and *Hamamelis* (Hamamelidaceae). In contrast to the wood of *Hamamelis*, short tangential banded parenchyma was not found in this sample. Therefore, we could identify it as *Schima* (Theaceae). *Schima wallichii* (DC.) Korthals, which grows in Japan, shows a similar wood anatomy, including the presence of helical thickening at the tips of vessel members and brown contents in the ray cells. However, the fossil is different in 1) more bars on scalariform perforation plates, 2) rays not as markedly heterocellular, and 3) more frequent uniseriate rays.

Stewartia beckeriana:

Similar to materials reported in Burgh 1978. The capsules show the following characters: 1) the mature capsules have a maximum length of 17 mm and a maximum width of 11 mm; 2) All capsules are pentamerous; 3) the longest stalk measured was 14 mm. The flower buds show the typical theaceous configuration: 5 thick leathery sepals and some cochleate petals. Kirchheimer (1957) united all the material earlier assigned to species of *Stewartia* or *Stuartia* under *S. beckeriana*. It is known from Pliocene deposits of various parts of Europe (Reid and Reid, 1915; Maidler, 1939; Szafer, 1947, 1954). The mature capsules have a maximum length of 17 mm and a maximum width of 11 mm. All

capsules are pentamerous. The longest stalk measured was 14 mm. The flower buds show the typical theaceous configuration: 5 thick leathery sepals and some cochleate petals. Kirchheimer (1957) united all the material earlier assigned to species of *Stewartia* or *Stuartia* under *S. beckeriana*. It is known from Pliocene deposits of various parts of Europe (Reid and Reid, 1915; Midler, 1939; Szafer, 1947, 1954).

Stewartia hokiana:

The leaves have several characteristics that indicate a close relationship to the genus *Stewartia*: oblong foliar shape, cremate-like margin that induced by vary short length of the apical side of the teeth, brochidodromous secondary veins that are arranged closely in the lower half of the lamina and form a series of loops in its distal part, weakly percurrent tertiary veins, and simple to once branched ultimate veinlets. These specimens closely related to the living *Stewartia pseudo-camellia* MAXIM. growing in Honshu to Kyushu of Japan. This new species is separable from *S. submonadelpha* Tanai et Onoe and from the extant *S. monadelpha* Sieb. et Zucc. by the large number of secondary veins in the lower half of the lamina.

Stewartia notoensis:

Prominent characters of these woods include: 1) diffuse-porous with almost exclusively solitary small vessels; 2) exclusively scalariform perforation plates and scalariform pitting of vessel walls; 3) diffuse and diffuse-in-aggregates axial parenchyma; 4) narrow heterocellular rays; 5) crystals in axial parenchyma strands. Similar woods are found in the Cornaceae, Theaceae, and Hamamelidaceae. In those families, characters such as almost exclusively solitary, thin-walled, rather circular vessels and diffuse and diffuse-in-aggregates axial parenchyma are present in *S. notoensis* and extant *Comus* L. (Cornaceae) and *Stewartia* L. (Theaceae). *Comus* usually has rays more than three cells wide, with high uniseriate wings and scalariform perforation plates with numerous bars. Therefore, we consider these fossils to be those of *Stewartia*.

Stewartia pseudocamellioxylon:

These fossils are characterized by 1) diffuse-porous wood consisting mostly of solitary narrow vessels, 2) exclusively scalariform perforation plates with 10–20 bars, 3) scalariform intervessel pits, 4) presence of tyloses in vessels, 5) diffuse or diffuse-in-aggregate axial parenchyma, and 6) heterocellular rays with 1–3 seriation. They have no crystals and have narrow rays being three cells wide. These features are the same as in extant species, especially those distributed in Korea and Japan, *S. koreana* and *S. pseudocamellia*. There have been some debates about whether or not the two extant species are the same species. Recent studies indicate that they are conspecific (Spongberg, 1974; Lee, 1987; Heo, 2001). Thus, at present, it seems appropriate to designate these fossils to a new species.

Stewartia stefanovii:

Shape lanceolate; base broad cuneate and slightly asymmetric; upper part acute; margin of lamina toothed, teeth starting near the base, strongly inclined and with rounded tips. Venations semicraspedodromous; midrib slightly arch-shaped, 1.5 mm thick at the base and strongly thinning at apex; secondary veins 10-12 pairs, forming an angle of 45-50° with midrib, consecutive and rarely opposite, arch-shaped, slightly distorted, forming 3-4 arches on the basal part after joining the preceding secondary vein; intercalary veins frequent; tertiary veins with numerous and their anastomoses forming the polygonal reticulum typical of the family. The lamina is 9.0-19.0 cm in length and 3.5-6.5 cm in width; petiolus 1.2 cm long and 0.2 cm wide. The fossil species shows a great morphological resemblance with the North American species *S. ovata* (Cav.) Weath.

Stewartia submonadelpha:

The fossil leaves of this species were first described in Japan, then it has been reported several times in Europe (Palamarev et al 2005). However, we do not have access to the original report by Tanai and Onoe (1961), so we here cited the description from Bozukov and Palamarev 1995. Shape elliptic, rarely narrow elliptic or ovate; base cuneate, sometimes asymmetrical; upper part most often thinning towards the apex, the nose which is formed varies in length reaching up to 2.0 cm; the margin of the lower part of lamina is complete, the margin of the upper part has more or less developed rare, small teeth. Venation semicraspedodromous; midrib slightly undulate, strongly thinning towards the apex; secondary veins 7-8 pairs, slightly arch-shaped, consecutive or opposing, forming an angle of 25-35° with the midrib and joining among themselves almost to the leaf margin; no intercalary veins are developed; tertiary veins hardly visible, arch-shaped or undulate, parallel, forming an angle of 70-90° with the secondary ones.

According to Tanai & Onoe (1961), the fossil species *Stewartia submonadelpha* has been known from the Late Tertiary flora of Mogi, Nagasaki Peninsula, SW Japan. The species possess certain polymorphism which falls within the limits of the recent Japanese species *S. monadelpha* Sieb. & Zucc. However, the geological epoch of the record in Japan is unclear. Therefore, we did not include this record in the biogeographical analysis.

Stewartia tertiaria:

Seeds without winged margin, of elongated obovate shape, flattened, asymmetrical, 2.3-4 mm long, 1.6-2.5 mm broad. Ornamentation very different on the dorsal and ventral surfaces; dorsal surface only punctate, finely pitted with few lateral wrinkles, ventral surface wrinkled due to branching of the irregular reticulum, testa thick, micropyle and hilum in close approximation on the cuneate base, funicular canal straight, dehiscence by two equally large flaps. Clearly differentiated from *S. lusatica* Mai by its essentially smaller size and the extreme ribbing on the ventral surface. The marked distinction in the ornamentation on the dorsal and ventral surfaces is shared with the seeds of *S. sinensis* Rehd. and Wils. (China: western Sichuan to northern Zhejiang). The seeds of this recent species are, however, significantly larger and have a narrowly winged margin. (Mai, 1998)

Justification: The fossil age was much older than the previous age estimation of crown *Stewartia* from molecular data. *Stewartia* was found to be a paraphyletic group. Because this fossil shares the same seed character (seeds without winged margin) with *Stewartia malacodendron*, the crown species of Stewartieae (*Stewartia s.l.*). We added the fossil to either the stem of Stewartieae or sister of *Stewartia malacodendron* or stem of Stewartia+Hartia.

References

- Li C., Wang C., Hsiao J., Yang C. 2003. Two Fossil Dicotyledonous Woods from the Kungkuan Tuff (Early Miocene), Northern Taiwan. *Flora*:67–70.
- Bozukov V., Palamarev E. 1995. On the Tertiary history of the Theaceae in Bulgaria. *Flora Mediterr.* 5:177–190.
- Burgh J. Van der. 1983. Allochthonous seed and fruit floras from the Pliocene of the lower rhine basin. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* 40:33–90.
- Burgh, J. Van der. 1978. The pliocene flora of fortuna-garsdorf I. fruits and seeds of angiosperms. *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology* 26:, 173–211.
- Choi S.-K., Kim K., Jeong E.-K., Terada K., Suzuki M., Uematsu H. 2010. Fossil Woods from the Miocene in the Yamagata Prefecture, Japan. *IAWA J.* 31:95–117.
- Deng L., Baas P. 1991. The Wood Anatomy of the Theaceae. *IAWA J.* 12:333–353.
- Grote P.J., Dilcher D.L. 1992. Fruits and Seeds of Tribe Gordonieae (Theaceae) from the Eocene of North America. *Am. J. Bot.* 79:744–753.
- Heo, K.I., 2001. Palynotaxonomic and numerical studies of trib. Stewartieae L. M.S. Thesis, Sungkyunkwan University, Seoul, Korea
- Huang L.-L., Jin J.-H., Quan C., Oskolski A.A. 2016. *Camellia nanningensis* sp. nov.: the earliest fossil wood record of the genus *Camellia* (Theaceae) from East Asia. *J. Plant Res.* 129:823–831.
- Jeong E.K., Kim K., Suzuki M., Kim J.W. 2009. Fossil woods from the Lower Coal-bearing Formation of the Janggi Group (Early Miocene) in the Pohang Basin, Korea. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* 153:124–138.
- Keng H. 1962. Comparative morphological studies in Theaceae. *Univ. Californ. Pub. Bot.*, 33(4): 264–384.
- Kovar-Eder J., Hably L. 2006. The flora of Mataschen - A unique plant assemblage from the Late Miocene of eastern Styria (Austria). *Acta Palaeobot.* 46:157–233.
- Kvaček Z. 2004. Revisions to the Early Oligocene flora of Flörsheim (Mainz Basin, Germany) based on epidermal anatomy. *Senckenbergiana lethaea.* 84:1–73.

- Kvaček Z., Walther H. 1984. Nachweis tertiärer Theaceen Mitteleuropas nach blatt-epidermalen Untersuchungen. I. Teil—Epidermale Merkmalskomplexe rezenter Theaceae. Feddes Repert. 95:209–227.
- Lee, S.T., 1987. A palynotaxonomic study on the Korean Theaceae. Kor. J. Bot. 30, 215–223.
- Li Y., Awasthi N., Yang J., Li C. Sen. 2013. Fruits of Schima (Theaceae) and seeds of Toddalia (Rutaceae) from the Miocene of Yunnan Province, China. Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol. 193:119–127.
- Maidler, K., 1939. Die pliozane Flora von Frankfurt am Main. Abh. Senckenb. Naturforsch. Ges., 446: 1--202.
- Mai DH. 1975. Über Früchte und Samen von Hartia Dunn (Theaceae). Friedrich-Schiller-Univ. Jena, Math.-Nat. 24: 463-476.
- Mai D.H. 1998. Contribution to the flora of the middle Oligocene Calau Beds. Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol. 101:43–70.
- Ozaki K. 1980. Late Miocene Tatsumitoge Flora of Tottori Prefecture, Southwest Honshu, Japan (III). Sci. Reports Yokohama Natl. Univ.:19–45.
- Palamarev E., Bozukov V., Uzunova K., Petkova A. 2005. Catalogue of the Cenozoic plants of Bulgaria. Phytol. Balc. 11:215–364.
- Reid, C. and Reid, E.M., 1915. The Pliocene floras of the Dutch--Prussian Border. Meded. Rijksopsporing Delfstoffen, 6 : 1--178.
- Shi X., Fu Q., Jin J., Quan C. 2017. Mummified Oligocene fruits of Schima (Theaceae) and their systematic and biogeographic implications. Sci. Rep. 7:4009.
- Sponberg, S.A., 1974. A review of deciduous leaved species of the Stewartia. J. Arnold Arb. 55, 182–214.
- Suzuki M., Terada K. 1996. Fossil wood flora from the lower Miocene Yanagida Formation, Noto Peninsula, Central Japan. IAWA J. 17:365–392.
- Szafer, W., 1947. The Pliocene flora of Kroscienko in Poland. Rozpr. Wydz. Matem. Przyrodniczego, 72B (2): 1--213.
- Szafer, W., 1954. Pliocene flora from the vicinity of Czorsztyn (West Carpathians) and its relationship to the Pleistocene. Inst. Geol. Prace, 11: 1--238.
- Tanai, T. & Onoe, T. 1961. A Mio- Pliocene flora from the Ningyô- tôte area on the border between Tottori and Okayama prefectures in Japan. – Rep. Geol. Surv. Japan, 187: 1-62.

Table S8. Comparison of the estimated ages of selected nodes obtained in this and previous studies. All ages in the table are in Ma; values in parentheses represent the 95% highest posterior density (HPD). Config1 refers to root age set to 109Ma and config2 refers to root age set to 125Ma.

Node	Config1	Config2	Yu et al. 2017	Lin et al. 2019	Rao et al., 2018
Pentaphylacaceae stem	82(77.6-91.4)	91.4(83.7-99.4)	80.8 (66.0-94.5)	-	-
Symplocaceae (Styracaceae) stem	79.6(74.7-87.9)	88.7(80.6-96)	79.9 (67.7-92.9)	-	-
Theaceae stem	82.5(77.8-91)	92.1(84.4-99.8)	88.5 (76.5-100.4)	-	89.8 (68.1-97.3)
Theaceae crown	58.8(52.6-67.2)	66.4(60-73.4)	52.7 (38.3-70.5)	-	59.6 (48.8-71.8)
Stewartieae crown	19.5(12.1-25.2)	22.6(15.1-28.7)	14.4 (8.1-23.7)	22.5 (17.9-27.4)	-
Stewartia ovata crown	13.3(8.8-18)	15.2(9.9-19.4)	-	17.3 (16.0-19.6)	-
Gordonieae (Theae) stem	56.4(50.4-65.5)	63.2(58-69.7)	45.5 (34.2-62.8)	-	50.2 (43.4-58.3)
Gordonieae crown	25.1(23.9-25.8)	25.6(24.1-26.4)	26.1 (23.4-31.8)	-	-
Gordonia crown	19.2(9.6-22.6)	20.8(12.6-22.8)	-	-	-
Franklinia crown	23.3(23.3-23.3)	23.3(23.3-23.3)	-	-	-
Schima stem	23.3(23.3-23.3)	23.3(23.3-23.3)	24.2 (23.0-28.6)	-	-
Schima crown	8.6(4.9-10.9)	9.4(6.7-11.6)	5.4 (1.9-11.0)	-	-
Theeae crown	20.6(13.5-26.4)	25.4(23.6-30)	19.8 (11.0-30.6)	-	-
Camellia (Polyspora) stem	19.6(13.4-26.1)	24.1(23.3-28.7)	13.7 (7.2-22.0)	-	-
Camellia crown	18.3(11.6-24.1)	21.6(16.7-28)	6.9 (3.7-11.9)	-	-
Pyrenria crown	11(7.6-14.1)	13.6(10.6-17.1)	-	-	-
Laplacea stem	19.5(12.6-25.1)	24.1(21.2-29.3)	-	-	-
Laplacea crown	10.1(6.5-13.9)	12.9(8.7-16.1)	-	-	-

References

- Rao M., Steinbauer M.J., Xiang X., Zhang M., Mi X., Zhang J., Ma K., Svenning J.C. 2018. Environmental and evolutionary drivers of diversity patterns in the tea family (Theaceae s.s.) across China. *Ecol. Evol.*:11663–11676.
- Yu X.Q., Gao L.M., Soltis D.E., Soltis P.S., Yang J.B., Fang L., Yang S.X., Li D.Z. 2017. Insights into the historical assembly of East Asian subtropical evergreen broadleaved forests revealed by the temporal history of the tea family. *New Phytol.* 215:1235–1248.
- Lin H.-Y., Hao Y.-J., Li J.-H., Fu C.-X., Soltis P.S., Soltis D.E., Zhao Y.-P. 2019. Phylogenomic conflict resulting from ancient introgression following species diversification in *Stewartia* s.l. (Theaceae). *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* 135:1–11.

Table S9. Comparison of DEC and DEC+j models for different datasets with maximum range size set to three.

Dataset	Model	LnL	Number of parameters	d	e	j	AICc	AICc_wt
nfossil	M0-DEC	-64.336±2.751	2	0.003±0.001	0±0	0±0	132.768±5.502	0.170
	M0-DEC+j	-61.407±1.88	3	0.002±0	0±0	0.01±0.002	129.008±3.76	0.830
	M1-DEC	-64.075±2.738	2	0.003±0.001	0±0	0±0	132.246±5.475	0.180
	M1-DEC+j	-61.243±1.882	3	0.002±0	0±0	0.01±0.002	128.68±3.765	0.820
fossil_10	M0-DEC	-96.717±4.2	2	0.007±0.001	0±0	0±0	197.523±8.4	0.003
	M0-DEC+j	-86.701±3.174	3	0.002±0.001	0±0	0.038±0.006	179.581±6.348	0.997

	M1-DEC	-96.008±4.244	2	0.006±0.001	0±0.001	0±0	196.105±8.489	0.002
	M1-DEC+j	-85.098±3.497	3	0.002±0.001	0±0	0.039±0.006	176.376±6.994	0.998
	M0-DEC	-123.829±5.442	2	0.009±0.001	0.001±0.001	0±0	251.74±10.884	0.001
	M0-DEC+j	-108.477±5.841	3	0.002±0.001	0.001±0	0.05±0.006	223.119±11.682	0.999
fossil_22	M1-DEC	-124.35±5.465	2	0.009±0.002	0.001±0.001	0±0	252.782±10.93	0.001
	M1-DEC+j	-109.489±5.621	3	0.002±0.001	0±0	0.05±0.007	225.143±11.241	0.999

Table S10. Comparison of biogeographic stochastic mapping result of main crown nodes across 300 phylogenies with maximum range size set to two. Abbreviations of phyloregions are as follows: N- Nearctic, P- Panamanian, E- Eurasia, S- Sino-Japanese, M- Papua-Melanesia. Recovered regions that occurred in more than 5% of the phylogenies are shown in the table.

Crown node	nfossil	fossil_10	fossil_22
M0-DEC			
Theaceae	NS: 95.3%	E: 32.7%, EN: 47.7%, ES: 15%	E: 25.8%, EN: 14.2%, ES: 10.3%, NS: 49.7%
Stewartieae	NS: 97%	E: 21.7%, EN: 70%	E: 20.6%, EN: 12.9%, ES: 60.6%
Gordonieae	NS: 96.3%	EN: 86%, N: 8%	EN: 11%, ES: 34.2%, NS: 50.3%
Theeae	PS: 44.9%, S: 55.1%	PS: 20%, S: 77.7%	S: 81.9%, PS: 14.2%
M0-DEC+j			
Theaceae	NS: 99.7%	E: 50.3%, EN: 31.3%, ES: 13.3%	E: 46.5%, EN: 18.7%, ES: 11%, NS: 23.9%
Stewartieae	NS: 97.7%	E: 65%, EN: 14.7%, N: 18%	E: 54.8%, ES: 12.9%, S: 27.1%
Gordonieae	NS: 68.4%, N: 24.3%, NP: 7.3%	E: 12.3%, EN: 12.3%, N: 71%	E: 36.1%, ES: 9.7%, NS: 25.2%, N: 25.8%
Theeae	S: 100%	S: 99.3%	S: 100%
M1-DEC			
Theaceae	NS: 95.7%	E: 32%, EN: 47.3%, ES: 16.3%	E: 14.9%, EN: 10.7%, ES: 13.2%, NS: 61.2%
Stewartieae	NS: 90%, N: 10%	E: 11.7%, EN: 75%, ES: 6.3%	E: 14.9%, EN: 19%, ES: 57%
Gordonieae	NS: 86.7%, NP: 13%	EN: 86.3%, N: 8.3%	EN: 8.3%, ES: 17.4%, NS: 71.1%
Theeae	PS: 76.1%, S: 23.9%	ES: 6%, S: 45.7%, PS: 48.3%	S: 82.6%, PS: 16.5%
M1-DEC+j			
Theaceae	NS: 99.3%	E: 42.3%, EN: 45.7%, ES: 5.3%, NS: 6.3%	E: 30.6%, EN: 38.8%, ES: 8.3%, NS: 22.3%
Stewartieae	NS: 98.3%	E: 40.7%, EN: 48.3%, N: 7.3%	E: 52.1%, ES: 12.4%, S: 32.2%
Gordonieae	NS: 65.8%, N: 14.3%, NP: 19.9%	EN: 19.7%, N: 73.3%	E: 17.4%, ES: 5.8%, NS: 19.8%, N: 51.2%

Theace PS: 8.6%, S: 91.4% S: 100% S: 100%

Table S11. Comparison of biogeographic stochastic mapping result of main crown nodes across 300 phylogenies with maximum range size set to three. Abbreviations of phyloregions are as follows: N- Nearctic, P- Panamanian, E- Eurasia, S- Sino-Japanese, M- Papua-Melanesia. Recovered regions that occurred in more than 5% of the phylogenies are shown in the table.

Crown node	nfossil	fossil_10	fossil_22
M0-DEC			
Theaceae	NPS: 37.7%, NS: 62%	ENP: 29%, EPS: 64.3%	E: 9.2%, ENP: 13.5%, ENS: 32.4%, EPS: 31.9%
Stewartieae	NS: 76.3%, N: 23.7%	ENS: 40.7%, EN: 47.7%	E: 6.5%, EN: 8.6%, ENS: 54.6%, ES: 24.3%
Gordoniaeae	NS: 72.7%, N: 12.3%, NP: 13.7%	ENP: 35.3%, ENS: 28.3%, EN: 29.7%	ENP: 9.2%, ENS: 68.1%, NS: 6.5%
Theace	PS: 39.7%, S: 60.3%	PS: 82.7%, S: 17.3%	PS: 48.6%, S: 47%
M0-DEC+j			
Theaceae	NS: 98.7%	EN: 28%, ENP: 5.7%, ENS: 37.7%, EPS: 21.3%	E: 18.4%, ENS: 71.9%, ES: 5.9%
Stewartieae	NS: 97%	E: 49.7%, EN: 16%, ENS: 17%, N: 6.3%, NS: 8.3%	E: 48.6%, ENS: 14.6%, ES: 9.7%, NS: 7%, S: 15.7%
Gordoniaeae	NS: 65%, N: 26.7%, NP: 6.7%	EN: 19%, ENP: 18.7%, N: 48.3%, NS: 6%	E: 17.8%, ENS: 15.7%, ES: 10.3%, NS: 37.8%
Theace	S: 100%	S: 85.7%, PS: 13.3%	S: 97.8%
M1-DEC			
Theaceae	NPS: 37.3%, NS: 62.3%	ENP: 30%, EPS: 64%	EN: 6.1%, ENP: 9.2%, ENS: 32.1%, EPS: 35.1%, NPS: 5.3%
Stewartieae	NS: 82.7%, N: 17.3%	ENS: 52.7%, EN: 33.7%	E: 6.9%, EN: 7.6%, ENS: 58.8%, ES: 16.8%, NS: 8.4%
Gordoniaeae	NS: 91.3%	ENP: 50%, ENS: 20.7%, EN: 24.3%	ENP: 13.7%, ENS: 64.9%, NS: 13%
Theace	PS: 70%, S: 30%	S: 18%, PS: 82%	PS: 65.6%, S: 31.3%
M1-DEC+j			
Theaceae	NS: 98.7%	E: 5.3%, EN: 29.3%, ENS: 37.7%, EPS: 21.7%	E: 14.5%, EN: 5.3%, ENS: 74%

Stewartieae	NS: 99%	E: 19.7%, EN: 31.7%, ENS: 32%, NS: 11.7%	E: 41.2%, ENS: 16%, ES: 7.6%, S: 24.4%
Gordonieae	NS: 58.3%, N: 23%, NP: 18.3%	EN: 26.7%, ENP: 20.7%, N: 41%, NS: 5.7%	E: 8.4%, ENS: 15.3%, NS: 55.7%, N: 6.1%
Theaeae	PS: 7.7%, S: 92.3%	S: 88%, PS: 10.7%	S: 99.2%

Figure S1.

Figure S1. Flowchart of the empirical Bayesian pipeline used in this study.

Figure S2.

Figure S2. Maximum likelihood (ML) bipartition tree inferred from plastid coding region matrix. Numbers associated with nodes indicate ML bootstrap support (BS)/Bayesian inference (BI) posterior probability (PP) values. Asterisks mark nodes with the highest support using both methods (bootstrap value 100% and posterior probability 1.0).

Figure S3.

Figure S3. Maximum likelihood (ML) bipartition tree inferred from nrDNA matrix. Numbers associated with nodes indicate ML bootstrap support (BS)/Bayesian inference (BI) posterior probability (PP) values. Asterisks mark nodes with the highest support using both methods (bootstrap value 100% and posterior probability 1.0).

Figure S4.

Figure S4. a) 50% consensus phylogeny of the randomly sampled 300 phylogenies with 10 fossil taxa added. b) The age interval of the added fossil taxa and the 95% confidence intervals of the estimated age of their corresponding genus and tribes.

Figure S5.

Figure S5. The reconstruction used DEC+j model under M0 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree based on only extant taxa (a) or based on both extant taxa and 10 fossil taxa (b). Colored circles at tips represent current ranges. Pie charts at inner nodes represent the average marginal probability of ranges across the 300 phylogenies and probabilities lower than 0.1 were combined and shown in white. Periods of forest types are divided following Meseguer et al. (2015). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using only extant taxa (c) or using both extant and 10 extinct taxa (d). One tick mark represents one dispersal event. The

lower panel show the source ranges and the upper panel show the sink ranges. The colored band within the lower panel show the sink ranges for each source range.

Figure S6.

Figure S6. The reconstruction used DEC model under M1 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. Annotations are the same as Figure S6. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree based on only extant taxa (a) or based on both extant taxa and 10 fossil taxa (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using only extant taxa (c) or using both extant and 10 extinct taxa (d).

Figure S7.

Figure S7. The reconstruction used DEC+j model under M1 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree based on only extant taxa (a) or based on both extant taxa and 10 fossil taxa (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using only extant taxa (c) or using both extant and 10 extinct taxa (d).

Fig S8.

Figure S8. The reconstruction incorporating information of 22 fossils under M0 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree using DEC model (a) or using DEC+j model (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using DEC model (c) or using DEC+j model (d).

Fig S9.

Figure S9. The reconstruction incorporating information of 22 fossils under M1 dispersal scenario with maximum number of occupied ranges set to two over 300 phylogenies. a-b. Average marginal probability of different areas mapped on the time-calibrated best RAxML-ng tree using DEC model (a) or using DEC+j model (b). c-d. Average number of reconstructed dispersals between different regions using DEC model (c) or using DEC+j model (d).

Figure S10.

Figure S10. The biogeographic reconstruction of the best tree using a reduced ancestral state space under M0 scenario using DEC model. Only adjacent ranges or single range were allowed (ES, EN, SM, NP, E, S, N, M, P).